

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

SELF EFFICACY COMMUNITY HEALTH WORKERS WITH CULTURAL DIVERSITY IN THE CONTEXT OF THE PUBLIC BEACHES, VALLEYS AND MOUNTAINS IN THE PROVINCE OF PAPUA

Agussalim¹, Masdiana AR², Gutit Enny Susanti³

¹Health Polytecnic of Jayapura, Nursing School, Jalan Padang Bulan 2, Hedam, Kota Jayapura, Papua, Indonesia, Telp: 006285757888449 E-mail:salim170878@gmail.com

²Health Polytecnic of Makassar, Nursing School, Jalan Bendungan Bili-bili, Makassar, Sulawesi Selatan, Indonesia

³Health Polytecnic of Jayapura, Nutritionist School, Jalan Padang Bulan 2, Hedam, Kota Jayapura, Papua, Indonesia

Abstract:

Culture is the work of a human being that is born along with the creation of man as well as a documented hereditary in accordance with periodization. Culture is born and develops and changes along with the changing times. The culture of a region will be very important against the level of development of public health in the region. The very culture played an important role in increasing the degree of the health of a community. The culture of the communities surrounding the areas health services must be understood by all health workers who will eventually have an impact to increase the health status of the community. This research aims to get an idea how health workers have good self-efficacy ability to culture communities in mountainous regions, the Valley, and the coast in the province of Papua. Variable; This research is divided into independent variables namely the culture of the community, the community's culture of the Valley, as well as the culture of the community in the coastal province of Papua and the Variable Dependently is the health officer self-efficacy Method; This research uses Multi Concurrent Design Method with Embedded Strategy approach where researchers use quantitative and qualitative methods together with the use of primary and secondary methods. The primary method used to obtain data, and a secondary method used to obtain data in support of the data obtained from the primary method. The research results obtained that about 32% who said very less confident and less confident as well as about 41% stating neutral in understanding the culture of Papua in the context of the public beaches, valleys and mountains. Discussion; the existence of these data gives an overview that the importance of supply self-efficacy about understanding the culture in which they will be on duty or placed in a working area which is suitable

Keywords: *Self efficacy, a health worker, community, culture of Papua.*

Corresponding author:**Agussalim,**

Health Polytecnic of Jayapura, Nursing School

Jalan Padang Bulan 2, Hedam, Kota Jayapura, Papua, Indonesia

Telp: 006285757888449 E-mail:salim170878@gmail.com

QR code

Please cite this article in press Agussalim et al., *Self Efficacy Community Health Workers With Cultural Diversity In The Context Of The Public Beaches, Valleys And Mountains In The Province Of Papua*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2018; 05(04).

I.INTRODUCTION:

Culture is the work of a human being that is born along with the creation of man as well as a documented hereditary in accordance with periodization. Culture is born and develops and changes along with the changing times. The progress of a nation, tribe and certain areas are very determined also by the culture of a region or tribe. The culture that evolved and well-documented currently has stored with a very sleek and modern. The culture has been stored in the file in the file such as micro soft film, flash drive, as well as computer files or laptop. The multiplicity of cultures in a specific area has become one of the references in the progress of a society or nation. The culture was born out of habit or the work of an individual or the community.

The culture of a region will be very important against the level of development of public health in the region. The very culture played an important role in increasing the degree of the health of a community. The culture of the communities surrounding the areas health services must be understood by all health workers who will eventually have an impact to the increase in the degree of health. Quality health services will have an increasing impact on the satisfaction of the public health care system.

In a study carried out by Evanny beautiful Clinics Pasundan 2013 obtained the result that out of 378 patients who performed the survey turns out they said that as many as 87.27% expressed dissatisfaction that in the show via a Cartesian diagram. Discussion of the results of such research it is recommended that clinics do the repair on the reliability, empathy and understanding of the local culture.

Based on research conducted by Arum Pratiwi and Siti Arifah in 2011 through the stages of analysis and qualitative content analysis identified the reason the behavior of pregnant women and childbirth is

associated with the culture to sustain the health of individuals and families, according to the perception of the family. Behavior that became worst when pregnant is abstinence should not be “kerokan”, should not be hot and drink when parturition is not to be the many motion until the 40th day, there can be a lot of drinking. While it is recommended when pregnant including drinking herbal medicine (jamu) is healthy and when parturition got others wear pilis, sitting straight and feet meeting and drinking herbal medicine. It is so illustrates that culture contributed towards improved health of pregnant women.

In the world of health that includes bio, psycho social, spiritual and soul which also play an important role in health order. In a Health Research Data base of the 2013 notes the prevalence of severe psychiatric in Indonesia reached 1.7 per mile. That is, 1-2 people from 1,000 inhabitants in Indonesia experienced severe psychiatric. According to Prof. Drs. Subandi, M.A, Ph.D by 2013, said the issue of mental health disorders and has the dimensions are quite complex. Mental health is not only a medical issue related or merely psychological, but it also has a socio-cultural dimension to spiritual and religious dimensions. Cultural factors can influence the onset and recurrence of the disorder of the soul, "he said while delivering the inaugural speech, Office of the great master in clinical psychology Faculty of psychology in the University Senate Hall at GADJAH MADA UNIVERSITY, Yogyakarta.

In progress now especially in the development of the region and globalization especially the era of ASEAN Community will require an accurate understanding will comparizon a culture because no doubt everything will result in cultural transactions between various regions, tribes, Nations, countries as well as transcontinental automated so that it takes the concept of transcultural (Agussalim, 2016).

Papua as a large area and is made up of many different tribes and spread in some areas of the mountains, the Valley and the beach certainly painted areas and different cultures. This will have a very significant role in the granting of health services in a community order and level of understanding of the local culture by practitioners of community health services.

2. Statement of The Problem

Based on the description above, so that the author is interested in better understanding self-efficacy community health workers against the cultural diversity in the context of the public beaches, valleys and mountains in the province of Papua 2016.

3. Purpose of Study

This research was compiled with the aim of: he knew the capabilities of self-efficacy health workers against the belief in the concept of culture and specific skills in papua on the community Beach, valleys, and mountains of 2016. He knows the ability of health workers in understanding about the cultural life of the community order and the beaches, valleys and mountains of 2016.

4. Research Design

The study has several definitions that are stated by the experts. One of them is as expressed by Narbuko and Ahmadi i.e. research is an activity objectively in an effort to discover and develop and test of science, based on the above principles, theories, arranged systematically through the intensive process in the development of generalizations. In this study, the method to be used by the author is a Concurrent Design

Method with Embedded Strategy approach where researchers use quantitative and qualitative methods together with the use of primary and secondary methods. The primary method used to obtain data, and a secondary method used to obtain data in support of the data obtained from the primary method.

The primary method is done by the method of interview in detail with community while the respondents to further strengthen the secondary method is done by using a cross cultural questioners has been validated by the method of statement by using liker scale. So the sample needed for quantitative research (secondary) this is as many as 89 people a health worker in the coastal areas, valleys, and mountains while for qualitative (primary) take a sample of 2 persons each clinics in three area of research. Sample primary method it represents an existing profession i.e. general practitioner, dentist, nurse, Dental Nurses, nutrition, environmental health, and Pharmaceutical Personnel.

Based on the conditions and extent of the region site is only done research in three areas, namely Sentani, Merauke, and Wamena with the total sample as much as 89 Sample consisting of Labor Nurses, doctors, nutrition, Sanitarian, pharmacy, dentist, Midwife, and laboratories. While the number of samples for research qualitative i.e. health workers as many as 12 in 6 clinics in 3 counties in the region of Papua Province.

5. RESULTS:

Self_efficacy ability of health workers against the belief in the concept of culture and special skills.

Table 1. Distribution of respondents based on the ability to distinguish cultural diversity.

Number	The ability to distinguish cultural diversity	Σ	%
1	Very Low Confidence	2	2%
2	Less Confidence	13	15%
3	Neutral	15	17%
4	Enough Confidence	47	53%
5	Very High Confidence	12	13%
Total		89	100%

Source: Primary Data 2016

Table 1 shows that out of 6 clinics with a total number of 89 people there were 2 respondents stating very less confident, 15 people being neutral, 13 people are less confident, 47 people who feel confident enough and 12 people very confident against the ability of distinguish cultural diversity. Most of the respondents have confidence against cultural diversity, because they are principled that they are health workers in charge of delivering health services regardless of cultural background which is multi-faceted.

Table 2. Distribution of respondents based on the ability to distinguish between tribalism and diskriminsi.

Number	The ability to distinguish between tribalism and diskriminsi	Σ	%
1	Very Low Confidence	1	1%
2	Less Confidence	14	16%
3	Neutral	22	25%
4	Enough Confidence	41	46%
5	Very High Confidence	11	12%
Total		89	100%

Source: Primary Data 2016

Table 2 shows that out of 6 clinics with a total number of 89 people there are 1 respondents who declared very less confident, 22 people being neutral, 14 people are less confident, 41 people who feel confident enough and 11 people very confident against the ability to distinguish between tribalism and diskrimination. Most of the respondents have confidence against cultural diversity, because they are principled that they are health workers in charge of delivering health services regardless of cultural background which is multi-faceted.

Table 3 distribution of respondents based on the ability to distinguish between ethnicity and culture

Number	he ability to distinguish between ethnicity and culture	Σ	%
1	Very Low Confidence	0	0%
2	Less Confidence	22	25%
3	Neutral	30	34%
4	Enough Confidence	28	31%
5	Very High Confidence	9	10%
Total		89	100%

Source: Primary Data 2016

Table 3 shows that out of 6 clinics with a total number of 89 people there are no respondents stating very less confident, 30 people being neutral, 22 people are less confident, 28 people are feeling quite confident and 9 people very confident against the ability to distinguish between ethnicity and culture. Most respondents are less able to distinguish between ethnicity and culture, because so many various cultures in New Guinea. Among existing tribes in Papua, there is a wide range of tribes that have the uniqueness of each.

Table 4 distribution of respondents based on the ability to use an interpreter in communication.

Number	The ability to distinguish cultural diversity	Σ	%
1	Very Low Confidence	3	3%
2	Less Confidence	14	16%
3	Neutral	30	34%
4	Enough Confidence	28	31%
5	Very High Confidence	14	16%
Total		89	100%

Source: Primary Data 2016

Table 4 shows that from 6 clinics with a total number of 89 people there are 3 respondents stating very less

confident, 30 people being neutral, 14 people are less confident, 28 people who feel confident enough and 14 people very confident against the ability to use an interpreter in communication. Respondents who could not understand the language used by the patient, using the assistance of an interpreter in the process of the services they provide. This is done to help the health worker in order to perform services optimally.

Table 5 distribution of respondents based on their ability to follow different tribal communities.

Number	The ability to distinguish cultural diversity	Σ	%
1	Very Low Confidence	6	7%
2	Less Confidence	17	19%
3	Neutral	39	44%
4	Enough Confidence	23	26%
5	Very High Confidence	4	4%
Total		89	100%

Source: Primary Data 2016

Table 5 shows that out of 6 clinics with a total number of 89 people there are 6 respondents stating very less confident, 23 people being neutral, 17 people are less confident, 23 people who feel confident enough and 4 people very confident against the ability to follow different tribal communities. Most of the respondents said neutral in terms of the ability to follow different tribal communities, because it takes an adjustment for the respondent to beradaptasi with the Customs and cultures of different tribes with them.

Table 6 distribution of respondents based on the capability of Providing protection.

Number	The ability to distinguish cultural diversity	Σ	%
1	Very Low Confidence	0	0%
2	Less Confidence	16	18%
3	Neutral	27	30%
4	Enough Confidence	39	44%
5	Very High Confidence	7	8%
Total		89	100%

Source: Primary Data 2016

Table 6 shows that out of 6 Clinics with a total number of 89 people there are no respondents stating very less confident, 27 people being neutral, 16 people are less confident, 39 people who feel confident enough and 7 people very confident against the ability of providing protection. Respondents largely expressed confidence to provide protection, because it feels it is his duty despite coming from different tribes with the patients they serve.

Table 7 distribution of respondents based on their ability to understand about diet for 24 hours.

Number	The ability to distinguish cultural diversity	Σ	%
1	Very Low Confidence	0	0%
2	Less Confidence	12	13%
3	Neutral	16	18%
4	Enough Confidence	47	53%
5	Very High Confidence	14	16%
Total		89	100%

Source: Primary Data 2016

Table 7 shows that out of 6 Clinics with a total number of 89 people there are no respondents stating very less confident, 16 people being neutral, 12 people are less confident, 47 people who feel confident enough and 14 people very confident against the ability of understanding about the patterns of eating for 24 hours. Most respondents understand the diet, this is understandable because the respondent was previously health officer has knowledge as well as gain insight into the pol.

Table 8. Distribution of respondents based on observing the ability of trainees.

Number	The ability of trainees	Σ	%
1	Very Low Confidence	1	1%
2	Less Confidence	15	17%
3	Neutral	42	47%
4	Enough Confidence	23	26%
5	Very High Confidence	8	9%
Total		89	100%

Source: Primary Data 2016

Table 8 shows that out of 6 Clinics with total number of 89 people there are 1 respondents who declared very less confident, 42 people being neutral, 15 people are less confident, 23 people who feel confident enough and 8 people very confident against observing capabilities of the participants.

Table 9: Distribution of respondents based on the ability to understand the life of every person.

Number	The ability to understand the life of every person	Σ	%
1	Very Low Confidence	4	5%
2	Less Confidence	19	21%
3	Neutral	27	30%
4	Enough Confidence	32	36%
5	Very High Confidence	7	8%
Total		89	100%

Source: Primary Data 2016

Table 9 shows that out of 6 Clinics with a total number of 89 people there were 4 people of respondents stating very less confident, 27 people being neutral, 19 people are less confident, 32 people who feel confident enough and 7 people very confident against the ability to understand the life of every person.

Table 10. Distribution of respondents based on their ability to develop a genealogy of life of each person.

Number	Ability to develop a genealogy of life of each person.	Σ	%
1	Very Low Confidence	3	3%
2	Less Confidence	16	18%
3	Neutral	39	44%
4	Enough Confidence	26	29%
5	Very High Confidence	5	6%
Total		89	100%

Source: Primary Data 2016

Table 10 shows that of the six Clinics with total number of 89 people 3 respondents stating very less confident, 39 people being neutral, 16 people are less confident, 26 people are feeling quite confident and 5 people very confident against the ability to develop life generation everyone.

The ability to understand about the order's cultural life

Distribution of respondents based on the ability to understand the order of family

Table 11. Community Beach

Number	The ability to understand the order of family	Σ	%
1	Very Low Confidence	11	12%
2	Less Confidence	12	13%
3	Neutral	20	23%
4	Enough Confidence	33	37%
5	Very High Confidence	13	15%
Total		89	100%

Source: Primary Data 2016

Table 11 shows that out of 6 Clinics with a total number of 89 people there are 11 respondents stating very less confident, 20 people being neutral, 12 people are less confident, 33 people who feel confident enough and 13 people are very confident against the ability of understanding familial order.

Table 12. Valley Community

Number	The ability to understand the order of family	Σ	%
1	Very Low Confidence	5	6%
2	Less Confidence	16	18%
3	Neutral	32	36%
4	Enough Confidence	24	27%
5	Very High Confidence	12	13%
Total		89	100%

Source: Primary Data 2016

Table 12 shows that out of 6 Clinics with a total number of 89 people there were 5 people respondents stating very less confident, 32 people being neutral, 16 people are less confident, 24 people who feel confident enough and 12 people very confident against the ability of understanding familial order.

Table 13. Mountain Community

Number	The ability to understand the order of family	Σ	%
1	Very Low Confidence	9	10%
2	Less Confidence	17	19%
3	Neutral	31	35%
4	Enough Confidence	20	13%
5	Very High Confidence	12	13%
Total		89	100%

Source: Primary Data 2016

Table 13. showed that of 6 Clinics with a total number of 89 people there were 9 people respondents stating very less confident, 31 people being neutral, 17 people are less confident, 20 people who feel confident enough and 12 people very confident against the ability of understanding familial order.

Distribution of respondents based on the ability to understand the role of differences within the family.

Table 14. Community Beach

Number	The ability to understand the role of differences within the family.	Σ	%
1	Very Low Confidence	3	3%
2	Less Confidence	15	17%
3	Neutral	22	25%
4	Enough Confidence	41	46%
5	Very High Confidence	8	9%
Total		89	100%

Source: Primary Data 2016

Table 14 shows that out of 6 Clinics with a total number of 89 people 3 respondents stating very less confident, 22 people being neutral, 15 people are less confident, 41 people who feel confident enough and 8 people very confident against the ability of understanding the differences in family roles.

Table 15. Valley Community

Number	The ability to understand the role of differences within the family	Σ	%
1	Very Low Confidence	4	5%
2	Less Confidence	10	11%
3	Neutral	37	41%
4	Enough Confidence	31	25%
5	Very High Confidence	7	8%
Total		89	100%

Source: Primary Data 2016

Table 15 shows that out of 6 Clinics with a total number of 89 people there were 4 people of respondents stating very less confident, 37 people being neutral, 10 people lack confidence, the 31 people who feel confident enough and 7 people very confident against the ability of understanding the differences in family roles.

Table 16. Mountain Community

Number	The ability to understand the role of differences within the family	Σ	%
1	Very Low Confidence	4	5%
2	Less Confidence	17	19%
3	Neutral	33	37%
4	Enough Confidence	26	29%
5	Very High Confidence	9	10%
Total		89	100%

Source: Primary Data 2016

Table 16 shows that out of 6 Clinics with a total number of 89 people there were 4 people of respondents stating very less confident, 33 people being neutral, 17 people are less confident, 26 people are feeling quite confident and 9 people very confident against the ability of understanding the differences in family roles.

Distribution of respondents based on the ability to understand the patterns of parenting.

Table 17. Community Beach

Number	The ability to understand the patterns of parenting	Σ	%
1	Very Low Confidence	3	3%
2	Less Confidence	11	12%
3	Neutral	33	37%
4	Enough Confidence	33	37%
5	Very High Confidence	9	10%
Total		89	100%

Source: Primary Data 2016

Table 17 shows that out of 6 Clinics with a total number of 89 people 3 respondents stating very less confident, 33 people being neutral, 11 people are less confident, 33 people are feeling quite confident and 9 people very confident against the ability to understand the patterns of parenting.

Table 18. Valley Community

Number	The ability to understand the patterns of parenting	Σ	%
1	Very Low Confidence	3	3%
2	Less Confidence	12	13%
3	Neutral	38	44%
4	Enough Confidence	26	29%
5	Very High Confidence	10	11%
Total		89	100%

Source: Primary Data 2016

Table 18 shows that out of 6 Clinics with a total number of 89 people 3 respondents stating very less confident, 38 people being neutral, 12 people are less confident, 26 people are feeling quite confident and 10 people very confident against the ability to understand the patterns of parenting.

Table 19. Mountain Community

Number	The ability to understand the patterns of parenting	Σ	%
1	Very Low Confidence	5	6%
2	Less Confidence	14	16%
3	Neutral	33	37%
4	Enough Confidence	25	28%
5	Very High Confidence	12	13%
Total		89	100%

Source: Primary Data 2016

Table 19 shows that out of 6 Clinics with a total number of 89 people in the community of the mountain there are 5 respondents stating very less confident, 33 people being neutral, 14 people are less confident, 25 people who feel confident enough and 12 people very confident against the ability to understand the patterns of parenting.

Distribution of respondents based on the ability to understand health system understanding.

Table 20. Community beach.

Number	The ability to understand health system understanding.	Σ	%
1	Very Low Confidence	3	3%
2	Less Confidence	15	17%
3	Neutral	25	28%
4	Enough Confidence	38	43%
5	Very High Confidence	8	9%
Total		89	100%

Source: Primary Data 2016

Table 20 shows that out of 6 Clinics with a total number of 89 on the community Beach man 3 respondents stating very less confident, 25 people being neutral, 15 people are less confident, 38 people who feel confident enough and 8 people very confident against the ability of understanding understanding of system health.

Table 21. Valley Community

Number	The ability to understand health system understanding.	Σ	%
1	Very Low Confidence	4	5%
2	Less Confidence	18	20%
3	Neutral	25	28%
4	Enough Confidence	35	39%
5	Very High Confidence	7	8%
Total		89	100%

Source: Primary Data 2016

Table 21 shows that out of 6 Clinics with a total number of 89 people on the msyarakat Valley there are 4 respondents stating very less confident, 25 people being neutral, 18 people are less confident, 35 people who feel confident enough and 7 people very confident against the ability to understand health system understanding.

Table 22. Mountain Community

Number	The ability to understand health system understanding.	Σ	%
1	Very Low Confidence	6	7%
2	Less Confidence	18	20%
3	Neutral	30	34%
4	Enough Confidence	27	30%
5	Very High Confidence	8	9%
Total		89	100%

Source: Primary Data 2016

Table 22 shows that out of 6 Clinics with a total number of 89 people on Mount msyarakat, there is a 6 person respondents stating very less confident, 30 people being neutral, 18 people are less confident, 27 people who feel confident enough and 8 people very confident against the ability of understanding understanding of system health. Distribution of respondents based on their ability to understand social support.

Table 23. Community Beach

Number	The ability to understand social support	Σ	%
1	Very Low Confidence	4	5%
2	Less Confidence	13	14%
3	Neutral	34	38%
4	Enough Confidence	34	38%
5	Very High Confidence	4	5%
Total		89	100%

Source: Primary Data 2016

Table 23 shows that out of 6 Clinics with a total number of 89 people on msyarakat coast there were 4 people of respondents stating very less confident, 34 people being neutral, 13 people are less confident, 34 people who feel confident enough and 4 people very confident against the ability of understanding the social support.

Table 24. Valley Community

Number	The ability to understand social support	Σ	%
1	Very Low Confidence	2	2%
2	Less Confidence	13	15%
3	Neutral	38	43%
4	Enough Confidence	29	32%
5	Very High Confidence	7	8%
Total		89	100%

Source: Primary Data 2016

Table 24 shows that out of 6 Clinics with a total number of 89 people on the msyarakat Valley there are 2 persons the respondents stating very less confident, 38 people being neutral, 13 people are less confident, 29 people who feel confident enough and 7 people very confident against the ability of understanding the social support.

Table 25. Mountain Community

Number	The ability to understand social support	Σ	%
1	Very Low Confidence	3	3%
2	Less Confidence	13	15%
3	Neutral	37	41%
4	Enough Confidence	31	35%
5	Very High Confidence	5	6%
Total		89	100%

Source: Primary Data 2016

Table 25 shows that out of 6 Clinics with a total number of 89 people on Mount msyarakat 3 respondents stating very less confident, 37 people being neutral, 13 people are less confident, 31 people are feeling quite confident and 5 people very confident against the ability of understanding the social support.

Distribution of respondents based on the ability to understand the utilization of traditional health practices.

Table 26. Community Beach

Number	The ability to understand the utilization of traditional health practices.	Σ	%
1	Very Low Confidence	1	1%
2	Less Confidence	14	16%
3	Neutral	35	39%
4	Enough Confidence	32	36%
5	Very High Confidence	7	8%
Total		89	100%

Table 26 shows that out of 6 Clinics with a total number of 89 people on msyarakat coast there is 1 non-respondents stating very less confident, 35 people being neutral, 14 people are less confident, 32 people who feel confident enough and 7 people very confident against the ability to understand the utilization of traditional health practices.

Table 27. Valley Community

Number	The ability to understand the utilization of traditional health practices	Σ	%
1	Very Low Confidence	2	2%
2	Less Confidence	12	13%
3	Neutral	34	38%
4	Enough Confidence	32	36%
5	Very High Confidence	9	10%
Total		89	100%

Table 27 shows that out of 6 Clinics with a total number of 89 people on the msyarakat Valley there are 2 persons the respondents stating very less confident, 34 people being neutral, 12 people are less confident, 32 people are feeling quite confident and 9 people very confident against the ability to understand the utilization of traditional health practices.

Table 28. Mountain Community

Number	The ability to understand the utilization of traditional health practices	Σ	%
1	Very Low Confidence	3	3%
2	Less Confidence	16	18%
3	Neutral	38	43%
4	Enough Confidence	25	28%
5	Very High Confidence	7	8%
Total		89	100%

Table 28 shows that out of 6 Clinics with a total number of 89 people on msyarakat Valley 3 respondents stating very less confident, 38 people being neutral, 16 people are less confident, 25 people who feel confident enough and 7 people very confident against the ability to understand the utilization of traditional health practices.

Distribution of respondents based on the ability to understand the patterns of nutrients.

Table 29. Community beach.

Number	The ability to understand the patterns of nutrients	Σ	%
1	Very Low Confidence	1	1%
2	Less Confidence	15	17%
3	Neutral	28	431%
4	Enough Confidence	37	42%
5	Very High Confidence	8	9%
Total		89	100%

Table 29 shows that out of 6 Clinics with a total number of 89 people on msyarakat coast there is 1 non-respondents stating very less confident, 28 people being neutral, 15 people are less confident, 37 people who feel confident enough and 8 people very confident against the ability to understand the patterns of nutrients.

Table 30 Valley Community

Number	The ability to understand the patterns of nutrients	Σ	%
1	Very Low Confidence	1	1%
2	Less Confidence	15	17%
3	Neutral	36	40%
4	Enough Confidence	30	34%
5	Very High Confidence	7	8%
Total		89	100%

Table 30 shows that out of 6 Clinics with a total number of 89 people on the msyarakat Valley there are 1 person respondents stating very less confident, 36 people being neutral, 15 people are less confident, 30 people who feel confident enough and 7 people very confident against the ability to understand the patterns of nutrients.

Table 31. Mountain Community

Number	The ability to understand the patterns of nutrients	Σ	%
1	Very Low Confidence	3	3%
2	Less Confidence	16	18%
3	Neutral	33	37%
4	Enough Confidence	29	33%
5	Very High Confidence	8	9%
Total		89	100%

Table 31 shows that out of 6 Clinics with a total number of 89 people on Mount msyarakat 3 respondents stating very less confident, 33 people being neutral, 16 people are less confident, 29 people who feel confident enough and 8 people very confident against the ability to understand the patterns of nutrients.

Distribution of respondents based on the ability to understand the lifestyle of economically.

Table 32. Community Beach

Number	The ability to understand the lifestyle of economically.	Σ	%
1	Very Low Confidence	0	0%
2	Less Confidence	12	13%
3	Neutral	30	34%
4	Enough Confidence	38	43%
5	Very High Confidence	9	10%
Total		89	100%

Table 32 shows that out of 6 Clinics with a total number of 89 people on msyarakat Coast there are no respondents stating very less confident, 30 people being neutral, 12 people are less confident, 38 people are feeling quite confident and 9 people very confident against the ability to understand the lifestyle of the economically

Table 33. Valley Community

Number	The ability to understand the lifestyle of economically.	Σ	%
1	Very Low Confidence	0	0%
2	Less Confidence	13	14%
3	Neutral	31	35%
4	Enough Confidence	38	42%
5	Very High Confidence	8	0%
Total		89	100%

Table 33 shows that out of 6 Clinics with a total number of 89 people in the community of the Valley there are no respondents stating very less confident, 31 people being neutral, 13 people are less confident, 38 people who feel confident enough and 8 people very confident against the ability to understand the lifestyle of economically.

Table 34 mountain community.

Number	The ability to understand the lifestyle of economically.	Σ	%
1	Very Low Confidence	1	1%
2	Less Confidence	17	18%
3	Neutral	32	36%
4	Enough Confidence	24	27%
5	Very High Confidence	10	11%
Total		89	100%

Table 34 shows that out of 6 Clinics with a total number of 89 people in the community of the mountain there are 1 person respondents stating very less confident, 32 people being neutral, 17 people are less confident, 24 people who feel confident enough and 10 people very confident against the ability to understand the lifestyle of economically. Distribution of respondents based on the ability to understand the patterns of displacement to another location.

Table 35 coastal Communities

Number	The ability to understand the patterns of displacement to another location.	Σ	%
1	Very Low Confidence	5	6%
2	Less Confidence	16	18%
3	Neutral	39	44%
4	Enough Confidence	21	23%
5	Very High Confidence	8	9%
Total		89	100%

Table 35 indicates that from 6 Clinics with a total number of 89 people on the public Beaches there are 5 respondents stating very less confident, 39 people being neutral, 16 people are less confident, 21 people who feel confident enough and 8 people very confident against the ability to understand the patterns of displacement to another location.

Table 36 Valley Community

Number	The ability to understand the patterns of displacement to another location.	Σ	%
1	Very Low Confidence	5	6%
2	Less Confidence	13	15%
3	Neutral	38	42%
4	Enough Confidence	26	29%
5	Very High Confidence	7	8%
Total		89	100%

Table 36 shows that out of 6 Clinics with a total number of 89 people in the community of the Valley there are 5 respondents stating very less confident, 38 people being neutral, 13 people are less confident, 26 people are feeling quite confident and 7 people very confident against the ability to understand the patterns of displacement to another location.

Table 37 mountain community

Number	The ability to understand the patterns of displacement to another location.	Σ	%
1	Very Low Confidence	9	10%
2	Less Confidence	13	15%
3	Neutral	38	42%
4	Enough Confidence	22	25%
5	Very High Confidence	7	8%
Total		89	100%

Table 37 shows that out of 6 Clinics with a total number of 89 people in the community of the mountain there are 9 respondents stating very less confident, 38 people being neutral, 13 people are less confident, 22 people are feeling quite confident and 7 people very confident against the ability to understand the patterns of displacement to another location.

Distribution of respondents based on the ability to understand the structure of classes in society.

Table 38 Community beach.

Number	The ability to understand the structure of classes in society.	Σ	%
1	Very Low Confidence	5	6%
2	Less Confidence	21	23%
3	Neutral	29	33%
4	Enough Confidence	24	27%
5	Very High Confidence	10	11%
Total		89	100%

Table 38 shows that out of 6 Clinics with a total number of 89 people on the public Beaches there are 5 respondents stating very less confident, 29 people being neutral, 21 people are less confident, 24 people who feel confident enough and 10 people very confident against the ability of understanding the structure of classes in society.

Table 39 Valley Community

Number	The ability to understand the structure of classes in society.	Σ	%
1	Very Low Confidence	3	3%
2	Less Confidence	20	23%
3	Neutral	38	43%
4	Enough Confidence	19	21%
5	Very High Confidence	9	10%
Total		89	100%

Table 39 indicates that from 6 Clinics with a total number of 89 people in the community of the Valley 3 respondents stating very less confident, 38 people being neutral, 20 people are less confident, 19 people are feeling quite confident and 9 people very confident against the ability of understanding the structure of classes in society.

Table 40 mountain community

Number	The ability to understand the structure of classes in society.	Σ	%
1	Very Low Confidence	3	3%
2	Less Confidence	22	25%
3	Neutral	39	44%
4	Enough Confidence	13	15%
5	Very High Confidence	12	13%
Total		89	100%

Table 40 shows that out of 6 Clinics with a total number of 89 people on mountain community 3 respondents stating very less confident, 39 people being neutral, 22 people are less confident, 13 people who feel confident enough and 12 people very confident against the ability of understanding the structure of classes in society.

Distribution of respondents based on the ability to understand the patterns related to the job.

Table 41 Community Beach

Number	The ability to understand the patterns related to the job.	Σ	%
1	Very Low Confidence	1	1%
2	Less Confidence	14	16%
3	Neutral	31	35%
4	Enough Confidence	33	37%
5	Very High Confidence	10	11%
Total		89	100%

Table 41 shows that out of 6 Clinics with a total number of 89 people on the coast there is a community of respondents stating very less confident, 31 people being neutral, 14 people are less confident, 33 people who feel confident enough and 10 people very confident against the ability understand patterns related to the job.

Table 42 Valley Community

Number	The ability to understand the patterns related to the job.	Σ	%
1	Very Low Confidence	1	1%
2	Less Confidence	10	11%
3	Neutral	41	46%
4	Enough Confidence	29	33%
5	Very High Confidence	8	9%
Total		89	100%

Table 42 shows that out of 6 Clinics with a total number of 89 people in the community of the Valley there is a respondent who stated very less confident, 41 people being neutral, 10 people are less confident, 29 people who feel confident enough and 8 people very confident against the ability understand patterns related to the job.

Table 43. Mountain community

Number	The ability to understand the patterns related to the job.	Σ	%
1	Very Low Confidence	2	2%
2	Less Confidence	14	16%
3	Neutral	26	29%
4	Enough Confidence	37	42%
5	Very High Confidence	10	11%
Total		89	100%

Table 43. shows that out of 6 Clinics with a total number of 89 people in the community of the mountain there are 2 persons the respondents stating very less confident, 26 people being neutral, 14 people are less confident, 37 people are feeling quite confident and 10 people very confident against the ability understand patterns related to the job.

Distribution of respondents based on the ability to understand the patterns that are associated with the disease.

Table 44 Community beach.

Number	The ability to understand the patterns that are associated with the disease.	Σ	%
1	Very Low Confidence	2	2%
2	Less Confidence	15	17%
3	Neutral	34	38%
4	Enough Confidence	31	35%
5	Very High Confidence	7	8%
Total		89	100%

Table 44 shows that out of 6 Clinics with a total number of 89 people on the public Beaches there are 2 persons the respondents stating very less confident, 34 people being neutral, 15 people are less confident, 31 people who feel confident enough and 7 people very confident against the ability to understand the patterns that are associated with the disease.

Table 45 Valley Community

Number	The ability to understand the patterns that are associated with the disease.	Σ	%
1	Very Low Confidence	3	3%
2	Less Confidence	18	20%
3	Neutral	34	38%
4	Enough Confidence	26	29%
5	Very High Confidence	8	9%
Total		89	100%

Table 45 shows that out of 6 Clinics with a total number of 89 people in the community of the Valley 3 respondents stating very less confident, 34 people being neutral, 18 people are less confident, 26 people are feeling confident enough and 8 people very confident against the ability to understand the patterns that are associated with the disease.

Table 46 mountain community

Number	The ability to understand the patterns that are associated with the disease.	Σ	%
1	Very Low Confidence	6	7%
2	Less Confidence	17	19%
3	Neutral	32	36%
4	Enough Confidence	24	27%
5	Very High Confidence	10	11%
Total		89	100%

Table 46 shows that out of 6 Clinics with a total number of 89 people in the community of the mountain there is a 6 person respondents stating very less confident, 32 people being neutral, 17 people are less confident, 24 people who feel confident enough and 10 people very confident against the ability to understand the patterns that are associated with the disease.

Distribution of respondents based on their ability to understand beliefs about health and illness.

Table 47 Beach Community

Number	The ability to understand beliefs about health and illness.	Σ	%
1	Very Low Confidence	5	6%
2	Less Confidence	16	18%
3	Neutral	18	20%
4	Enough Confidence	40	45%
5	Very High Confidence	10	11%
Total		89	100%

Table 47 shows that out of 6 Clinics with a total number of 89 people on the public Beaches there are 5 respondents stating very less confident, 18 people being neutral, 16 people are less confident, 40 people are feeling quite confident and 10 people very confident against the ability understand beliefs about health and illness.

Table 48 Valley Community

Number	The ability to understand beliefs about health and illness.	Σ	%
1	Very Low Confidence	4	4%
2	Less Confidence	22	25%
3	Neutral	24	27%
4	Enough Confidence	27	30%
5	Very High Confidence	12	13%
Total		89	100%

Table 48 shows that out of 6 Clinics with a total number of 89 people in the community of the Valley there are 4 respondents stating very less confident, 24 people being neutral, 22 people less confident, 27 people who feel confident enough and 12 people very confident against the ability understand beliefs about health and illness.

Table 49 mountain community

Number	The ability to understand beliefs about health and illness.	Σ	%
1	Very Low Confidence	7	8%
2	Less Confidence	24	27%
3	Neutral	24	27%
4	Enough Confidence	21	23%
5	Very High Confidence	13	15%
Total		89	100%

Table 49 shows that out of 6 Clinics with a total number of 89 people on mountain community there is 7 people respondents stating very less confident, 24 people being neutral, 22 people less confident, 21 people who feel confident enough and 13 people are very confident against the ability understand beliefs about health and illness. Distribution of respondents based on their ability to understand beliefs about honour and rights.

Table 50. Community Beach

Number	The ability to understand beliefs about honour and rights.	Σ	%
1	Very Low Confidence	4	4%
2	Less Confidence	12	13%
3	Neutral	28	32%
4	Enough Confidence	34	39%
5	Very High Confidence	11	12%
Total		89	100%

Table 50 shows that out of 6 Clinics with a total number of 89 people on the public Beaches there are 4 respondents stating very less confident, 28 people being neutral, 12 people are less confident, 34 people who feel confident enough and 11 people very confident against the ability understand beliefs about honour and rights.

Table 51. Valley Community

Number	The ability to understand beliefs about honour and rights.	Σ	%
1	Very Low Confidence	4	4%
2	Less Confidence	10	11%
3	Neutral	29	33%
4	Enough Confidence	23	26%
5	Very High Confidence	17	19%
Total		89	100%

Table 51 indicate that from 6 Clinics with a total number of 89 people in the community of the Valley there are 4 respondents stating very less confident, 29 people being neutral, 10 people are less confident, 23 people who feel confident enough and 17 people are very confident against the ability understand beliefs about honour and rights.

Table 52. Mountain Community

Number	The ability to understand beliefs about honour and rights.	Σ	%
1	Very Low Confidence	4	4%
2	Less Confidence	10	11%
3	Neutral	35	40%
4	Enough Confidence	23	26%
5	Very High Confidence	17	19%
Total		89	100%

Table 52 shows that out of 6 Clinics with a total number of 89 people in the community of the mountain there are four respondents stating very less confident, 29 people being neutral, 10 people are less confident, 23 people who feel confident enough and 17 people are very confident against the ability understand beliefs about honour and rights.

Distribution of respondents based on their ability to understand convictions against decency.

Table 53 Beach Community

Number	The ability to understand convictions against decency.	Σ	%
1	Very Low Confidence	0	0%
2	Less Confidence	7	8%
3	Neutral	26	29%
4	Enough Confidence	38	43%
5	Very High Confidence	18	20%
Total		89	100%

Table 53 shows that out of 6 Clinics with a total number of 89 people on the public beaches there are no respondents stating very less confident, 26 people being neutral .7 people less confident, 38 people are feeling quite confident and 18 people are very confident against the ability understand beliefs against decency.

Table 54. Valley Community

Number	The ability to understand convictions against decency	Σ	%
1	Very Low Confidence	2	2%
2	Less Confidence	6	7%
3	Neutral	34	39%
4	Enough Confidence	31	35%
5	Very High Confidence	16	18%
Total		89	100%

Table 54 shows that out of 6 Clinics with a total number of 89 people in the community of the Valley there are 2 respondents stating very less confident, 34 people being neutral, 6 people lack confidence, the 31 people who feel confident enough and 16 people are very confident against the ability understand beliefs against decency.

Table 55. Mountain Community

Number	The ability to understand convictions against decency	Σ	%
1	Very Low Confidence	3	3%
2	Less Confidence	11	12%
3	Neutral	34	38%
4	Enough Confidence	30	34%
5	Very High Confidence	11	12%
Total		89	100%

Table 55 shows that out of 6 Clinics with a total number of 89 people in the community of the mountain there are three respondents stating very less confident, 34 people being neutral, 11 people are less confident, 30 people who feel confident enough and 11 people very confident against the ability understand beliefs against decency.

Distribution of respondents based on their ability to understand religious beliefs and examples that follow.

Table 56. Community beach.

Number	The ability to understand religious beliefs and examples that follow.	Σ	%
1	Very Low Confidence	0	0%
2	Less Confidence	12	13%
3	Neutral	14	16%
4	Enough Confidence	43	49%
5	Very High Confidence	20	22%
Total		89	100%

Table 56 shows that out of 6 Clinics with a total number of 89 people on the public beaches there are no respondents stating very less confident, 14 people being neutral, 12 people are less confident, 43 people who feel confident enough and 20 people very confident against the ability understand religious beliefs and examples that follow.

Table 57. Valley Community

Number	The ability to understand religious beliefs and examples that follow.	Σ	%
1	Very Low Confidence	2	2%
2	Less Confidence	8	9%
3	Neutral	24	27%
4	Enough Confidence	39	44%
5	Very High Confidence	16	18%
Total		89	100%

Table 57 shows that out of 6 Clinics with a total number of 89 people in the community of the Valley there are 2 respondents stating very less confident, 24 people being neutral, 8 people are less confident, 39 people who feel confident enough and 16 people are very confident against the ability of understanding the religious beliefs and the examples that follow.

Table 58. Mountain Community

Number	The ability to understand religious beliefs and examples that follow.	Σ	%
1	Very Low Confidence	2	2%
2	Less Confidence	7	8%
3	Neutral	29	33%
4	Enough Confidence	34	38%
5	Very High Confidence	17	19%
Total		89	100%

Table 58 shows that out of 6 Clinics with a total number of 89 people in the community of the mountain there are 2 respondents stating very less confident, 29 people being neutral, 7 people are less confident, 34 people who feel confident enough and 17 people are very confident against the ability of understanding the religious beliefs and the examples that follow.

6. DISCUSSION:

Self_efficacy ability of health workers against the belief in the concept of culture and special skills.

On the distribution of the respondents based on the ability to distinguish cultural diversity to Papua there is a statement as much as 17% are less confident and very less confident and there are 15 respondents who answered the neutral sample of 89. This indicates that it is still very low so the ability of health care personnel who are in the territory of papua in understanding of the existence of the culture of the local community.

As for the ability of health workers in distinguishing between sukuisme and discrimination there is 17% which is at a negative level, namely a sense of confidence and not very confident while saying neutral is 25% in understanding health services within the context of the existing sukuisme in New Guinea. For community health workers in the ability to distinguish between ethnicity and cultures in New Guinea there are as much as 25% which is at the level of very less confident and less confident as well as stating neutral or no answer as much as 34% in understanding how the ethnic presence in the territory of Papua. Lack of understanding in the presence of

ethnicity will become obstacles in delivering health services are holistic. This theory of Kuntjaranigrat in 1997, saying that the ethnic community within a group is very influential towards the improvement of the degree of the health of a community.

Whereas community health workers how to use an interpreter in communication from 89 in three sample regions of Papua in discover there are 19% who have a statement less confident and very less confident as well as 34% stating neutral. This is in line with an embedded interview from mountain region that says "I am not confident in communicating with local communities that originate from the Interior of much if I don't have a translator or an interpreter who can understand them".

Whereas community health workers how to follow different tribal culture in the Ministry of health in the get that there was approximately 26% who gave a negative statement that is very less confident and less confident as well as the 44% who have no options or neutral in intermingling with the culture of the local community and is in line with an embedded interview who said that "the bustle and fear in diskomunikasi that make that slow the process implemented intermingling".

There are 18% who have a statement less confident and very less confident as well as 30% who do not understand or neutral nature of related health workers in delivering health protection within the context of health services. While their ability in understanding society's diet for 24 hours from 89 sample there are approximately 13% who say that very less confident and less confident and as much as 18% stating neutral. For observing the trainee, as much as 18% who say less confident and very less confident as well as 47% stating neutral in providing training and observing the activities that are undertaken by a health workers against the local people.

The ability of health workers in the ability to understand his client's life history in which they served there are 26% who say it is very less confident and less confident and as much as 30% stating neutral or without statement of the 89 existing sample. While the ability of health workers in developing each person's living lineage in the context of communities who say very less confident and less confident in understanding such thing that is as much as 21% and 44% stating neutral or without a statement.

Elaboration of the data above, it found that the high number of taste less confident, very less confident, and there are no options or neutral in the understanding of self_efficacy in cross cultural health

workers in Papua. This is an issue that could have an effect on the increase in the degree of health as related to the ability of health workers against understanding local culture and does not have a strong confidence in understanding the local culture. It is also in line with what the Bandura (1997) which says that self_efficacy is the generative ability of individual-owned include cognitive, social, and emotional.

It is also played by Bandura and Jourden (1991) that doubt can affect individual capabilities so that the ability does not appear, because of doubts that it can weaken the confidence to achieve a particular goal. This should get the attention of a great many policies to place health workers should do the training increased self efficacy against a cultural environment where they will be on duty.

The ability to understand about the order's cultural life.

Research done on how community health workers to understand the order of three related areas of cultural life in Papua that is Beaches, valleys and mountains. Understanding health workers about the familial order at masyarakat Beach which States very less confident and less confident as much as 25%, neutral as much as 23% while the Valley communities 24% and 36%, while confidence and lacking confidence in the community of the mountains as much as 29% and neutral as much as 35%.

The confidence which is very less and less understanding of difference once the role within the family to the Beach Community 20% neutral, and as much as 25% whereas the community of the Valley as much as 165 and 41%, while mountain communities as much as 24% and 37%. The ability to understand the patterns of parenting which States very less confident and less confident as well as stating the neutral on the public beach is 15% and 37%, 26% and Valley communities 44%, and 22% mountain communities as well as 37%.

The ability of health workers to understand pemahaman the health system on the public beach that States less confident and less confident as much as 20% and neutral as much as 28%, for the communities of the Valley that is 25% and 28%, as well as mountain communities as much as 27% and 34%. As for understanding health workers related to their understanding of social support on the public beach with a statement very less confident and less confident as much as 19% and stating neutral as much as 38%, 17% and Valley communities 43% and mountain community that is 18% and 41%.

The ability of community health workers to the utilization of traditional health practices on a coastal community which States very less confident and less confident as much as 17%, and 39% stating neutral, while for the communities of the Valley as much as 15% and 38%, while mountain communities as much as 21% and 43%. While the ability of health workers to understand patterns of nutrients in coastal communities are less confident and less confident as much as 18%, and cannot comment at all or neutral as much as 31% while for the communities of the Valley that is 18% and 40% as well as the mountain community that is 21% and 37%.

As much as 13% for very less confident and less confident as well as 34% felt neutral or do not have the answer to understanding health workers in understanding economic lifestyle on health workers in coastal areas and around 14% and 35% in the community of the Valley as well as 19% and 36% in the community.

The ability of health workers to understand the patterns of displacement in other kelokasi where very less confident and less confident on the public beaches as much as 24% and that do not have an opinion or a neutral nature as much as 44% and sebnyak Valley Community 21% and 42% while in the mountain community of 25% and 42%. While the ability to understand the structure of classes in communities for coastal regions with very less confident and less confident as much as 29% and neutral as much as 33%, while for the communities of the Valley as much as 26% and 43%, and the community of the mountains was 28% and 44%. Forms of understanding executed with very less confident and less confident related ability to understand work-related patterns in the coastal communities as much as 17% and that said as many as 35% is neutral, while for the community of the Valley that is as much as 12% and 46%, but for society as well as the mountains as much as 18% 29%.

While the ability to understand the patterns that are associated with the disease on the public beach where 19% stating very less confident and less confident while stating there are neutral as much as 38% and the communities of the Valley as much as 23% and 38%, while for mountain communities as much as 26% and 36%. To the ability of health workers to understand beliefs about health and illness as much as 24% to statement is very less confident and less confident and 20% stating neutral or no statement for the community and for the community Beach Valley

i.e. 29% and 27% for the community as well as the mountains as much as 35% and 27%.

Related responden distribution understanding beliefs about honour and rights with a statement very less confident and less confident on the public beaches as much as 17% and 32% neutral stating as much at the public beach, and the community of the Valley as much as 15% and 33%, while for mountain communities as much as 15% and 40%. While an understanding of the ability to understand the beliefs against decency to coastal communities stated very less confident and less confident that is 8% and 29% stating neutral or without comment. For the community in the Valley as much as 9% and 39% while for mountain communities as much as much as 15% and 38%.

As for the ability of religious belief and understanding the examples that follow to the public beach with very less confident and less confident as much as 13% and 16% for a no commitment or neutral, whereas in the community of the Valley as much as 9% and 27% and mountain communities as much as 8% and 33%.

Based on the above data elaboration very significant associated health worker's ability in understanding familial order communities in the context of the public beaches, valleys and mountain communities. The taste is very lacking confidence to no statement which is neutral as a negative sign signifies by health workers in the understanding of the family order in the territory of Papua. This gives the explanation that the process of adaptation and the readiness of health workers in the concept of self-confidence is very less and need a sustainable intervention.

REFERENCES:

1. Agussalim. (2016). Cross Cultural Adaptation and Validation of Self_efficacy Scale of Papua Nurses Among ASEAN Country, IJSR, India.
2. Agussalim. (2015), Transcultural Nursing, Masyarakat Ekonomi ASEAN, dan Caring serta Latihan critical Thinking. Fitramaya, Yogyakarta.
3. BPPSDM. (2015). Pembinaan Wilayah Kementerian Kesehatan Di Provinsi Papua, Kementerian Kesehatan Republik Indonesia., Jakarta.
4. Indah, Evanny. (2013), Gambaran Tingkat Kepuasan Pasien Terhadap Pelayanan Kesehatan di Puskesmas Pasundan Kota Bandung, Universitas Pajajaran, Bandung.
5. Fakultas Psikologi UGM. (2015). Budaya dan Agama Pengaruhi Kesehatan Jiwa, Humas UGM, Yogyakarta.

6. Modouw, James. (2013). Pendidikan dan Peradaban Papua, Suatu Tinjauan Kritis
7. Transformasi Sosial, Bajawa Press, Jakarta.
8. Sari Tilawati, Defrina. (2013), Pengaruh Penggunaan Media Pembelajaran Terhadap Motivasi Belajar Siswa pada Pelajaran Akuntansi, Universitas Pendidikan Indonesia, Jakarta.
9. Sugiyono. (2014), Metode penelitian kuantitatif, kualitatif, dan R&D , Alpa beta, Bandung.
10. Sulistyono dan Basuki. (2005), Metodologi Kuantitatif dan Kualitatif dalam penelitian ilmu perpustakaan dan informasi, Arist.
11. P, Arum dan Sitti Arifah. (2011), Perilaku Kehamilan, Persalinan dan Nifas terkait dengan Budaya Kesehatan Pada Masyarakat Jawadi Wilayah Kabupaten Sukoharjo, Jurnal Komunikasi Kesehatan (edisi 2) P3M Akbid Purworejo.